

Appendices

Appendix A: Univariate Moran's I Statistics for all Dependent Variables (Block Unit of Analysis)

Dependent variable	Univariate Moran's I	Z-score
Total missing persons cases- all	0.464*	72.432
Total missing persons cases- SIP	0.465*	74.237
Total missing persons cases- non-SIP	0.460*	71.762
Open missing persons cases- all	0.447*	67.771
Open missing persons cases- SIP	0.464*	70.187
Open missing persons cases- non-SIP	0.440*	66.915
Found missing persons cases- all	0.472*	75.203
Found missing persons cases- SIP	0.433*	68.686
Found missing persons cases- non-SIP	0.472*	74.897

Note: * $p = 0.001$